

MASTER'S THESIS

Chatbot Generation Using Software Product Line Techniques: A Systematic Approach for Reusing Domain Artifacts

By
José Antonio Zamudio Amaya

To obtain the title of
Master in Software Engineering: Cloud, Data and IT
Management

Directed by
David Benavides Cuevas
Jordi Cabot Sagrera

Presented at the University of Seville, Spain

June, 2022/23

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deep appreciation to my advisors, David Benavides and Jordi Cabot, for their guidance, support, and invaluable insights throughout my research. Their extensive knowledge and expertise in the field have been instrumental in shaping the direction of this work. Their constructive feedback and continuous encouragement have helped me to push my limits and strive for excellence.

I would also like to thank my family for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout my academic journey. Their love and belief in me have been a source of motivation and inspiration, and I am deeply grateful for their presence in my life.

I would like to extend my gratitude to José Ángel Galindo, my previous advisor, for his support and guidance since I joined the research team. His contributions have been instrumental in shaping my research interests and laying the foundation for this project. I am also grateful to my lab partners. Their dedication and hard work have been an inspiration to me.

Finally, I would like to acknowledge my beloved lovebird pet, Dino, for being a constant source of joy and companionship during the writing process. His cheerful presence and playful antics have provided a much-needed break from the rigours of research, and I am grateful for his love and affection.

Resumen

Los chatbots han ganado cada vez más popularidad en diversos sectores, ya que proporcionan un medio para automatizar las interacciones con los participantes, reduciendo la carga de trabajo y mejorando la eficiencia. Sin embargo, desarrollar un chatbot con un alto nivel de precisión y personalización puede llevar mucho tiempo y, en la actualidad, no existe un proceso sistemático para reutilizar de forma eficiente la información de dominio para agilizar este proceso. Para superar este reto, proponemos una solución que aplica técnicas de ingeniería de línea de producto sobre el proceso de generación de chatbot para generar familias de chatbots que comparten características entre sí, incluidas las intenciones del usuario, los agentes de procesamiento del lenguaje natural y otras características relevantes, para integrarlos en los chatbots. Además, se muestra una herramienta que aplica los conceptos discutidos en este proyecto y que ofrece una solución práctica que podría servir para mejorar la eficacia y la eficiencia del desarrollo de chatbots.

Keywords: líneas de producto software, chatbots, reutilización de artefactos de dominio

Abstract

Chatbots have become increasingly popular in a variety of industries as they provide a means to automate interactions with participants, reducing workload and improving efficiency. However, developing a chatbot with a high level of accuracy and customization can be time-consuming and, currently, there is no systematic process for efficiently reusing domain information to streamline this process. To overcome this challenge, we propose a solution that applies product line engineering techniques on the chatbot generation process to generate families of chatbots that share features with each other, including user intents, natural language processing agents, and other relevant features, for integration into chatbots. In addition, a tool is shown that applies the concepts discussed in this project and offers a practical solution that could serve to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of chatbot development.

Keywords: software product lines, chatbots, domain artifact reusability

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Part I

INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

This master thesis presents a solution to reuse domain artifacts and to apply product line engineering techniques to chatbot generation. Research is conducted under the guidance of two experts in the field of software engineering, Dr. David Benavides and Dr. Jordi Cabot.

Dr. David Benavides is a full professor at the University of Seville and is renowned for his research on Software Product Lines, software variability, and highly configurable systems. I had the opportunity to work with him during both my degree thesis and my master's thesis, where we explored the application of Software Product Line Engineering. Since then, I have continued to collaborate with him, focusing on developing efficient and effective software engineering solutions.

Dr Jordi Cabot is the head of the Software Engineering Unit at the ITIS department of the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology. He is renowned for his research in software modeling, model-driven engineering, and software language engineering. His work on modeling techniques and tools has contributed significantly to the advancement of software engineering practices. During this Master's thesis, I have had the great opportunity to collaborate with him, whose expertise has helped me to solidify key concepts, techniques, and procedures in the world of research.

In this thesis, two frameworks are employed. The first framework, FLAMA, focuses on feature model validation. Developed by Dr. David Benavides and his research team, FLAMA has been instrumental in ensuring the correct use of feature models and SPL techniques. The second framework utilized in this thesis is Xatkit, developed by Dr. Jordi Cabot's team. Xatkit is specifically designed for chatbot generation, providing a comprehensive set of tools and capabilities. Moreover, it provides many different capabilities, like NLP services or intent recognition modules thus leveraging the chatbot generation process.

By combining the contributions of both frameworks, this master's thesis aims to make a distinct and impactful contribution to the field. Research explores the integration of FLAMA's model validation capabilities and Xatkit's chatbot generation techniques, leveraging the strengths of each framework to optimize the process of chatbot development. This approach could enable the creation of chatbots that not only meet high-quality standards but also exhibit enhanced functionality and adaptability within specific domains.

1.1. Context and motivation

Rapid advances in artificial intelligence and natural language processing have led to a surge in the popularity of chatbots in recent years. As a software engineering enthusiast, I was intrigued by the potential of chatbots to automate interactions and reduce workload in various industries. This motivated me to further explore the development of chatbots and deepen my knowledge in this area.

During my research, I came across the contributions of Dr. Jordi Cabot in this field. His work on chatbot creation using modeling techniques while promoting the rigorous use of software models in all software tasks caught my attention, and I was fascinated by his research. I found that both Dr. Cabot and my current advisor, Dr. Benavides, had collaborated previously on some research projects. This led me to arrange a meeting with them and express my interest in working with both of them on a project that combined software product lines, software engineering, and chatbot development. I am grateful that they agreed to be my advisors and provided guidance and support throughout this master’s thesis.

The main motivation behind this Master’s thesis project was to make a significant contribution to the chatbot development area. Through our research, we identified several shortcomings and gaps in the current approaches to chatbot development. After conducting a thorough literature review, we found that while there are many existing tools and approaches to chatbot development, none of them addresses the issue of efficiently reusing domain information.

The importance of chatbots in the present landscape cannot be overstated, and their importance is poised to grow even further in the future. With the ever-increasing demand for personalized and efficient user interactions, chatbots have emerged as valuable tools across various industries. However, the current approach of individually crafting chatbots without considering the potential for reuse and shared resources, such as databases and knowledge bases, represents a missed opportunity for optimization and scalability.

1.2. Problem description

In the rapidly evolving field of chatbot development, the lack of a practical solution for reusing already existing domain artifacts poses a significant challenge. Domain artifacts encompass databases, documents, pre-trained models, and other sources of information that contain valuable knowledge and resources specific to a particular domain or industry. The absence of a systematic approach for reusing domain artifacts necessitates a time-consuming manual integration process. Developers must invest considerable effort in extracting, transforming, and loading the relevant information from various sources into each chatbot project. This process is prone to errors and inconsistencies, as it heavily relies on human intervention and manual data manipulation. Moreover, if we need to create several different chatbots, this process has to be repeated over and over. Figure 1.1 illustrates the current approach for generating multiple chatbots.

Due to the lack of a standardized approach, chatbots developed independently without reusing domain artifacts can exhibit inconsistencies in their responses, knowledge base, and user experience. For instance, different chatbots within an organization may provide conflicting answers to the same user query or lack uniformity in their branding and interaction style. These inconsistencies undermine the overall quality and reliability of the chatbot ecosystem. The absence of a practical solution to systematically reuse information artifacts necessitates redundant efforts in sourcing, processing, and integrating domain-specific knowledge into each chatbot project. This significantly prolongs the development cycle and incurs additional costs for organiza-

Figure 1.1: Creating two chatbots based on the same domain artifacts

tions. Furthermore, the potential for errors during manual integration amplifies the need for thorough testing and debugging, further adding to the development time and cost.

1.3. Contribution

To address the identified problem, we propose a systematic approach for facilitating chatbot generation through the reuse of domain artifacts by applying product line engineering techniques, since they excel at reusing domain information and core assets (for references, see section 3). The proposal uses feature-modeling techniques to model intent variability in chatbots. We also have developed a tool for chatbot generation based on our approach, in order to demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed approach. It is designed to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of chatbots by enabling the integration of relevant domain information, including user intentions, natural language processing agents, and other relevant features.

The tool is built on top of Xatkit¹, an open-source platform to build chatbots. The Xatkit DSL provides an intuitive interface to build chatbots. Additionally, we utilized FLAMA², a model analysis framework, to perform validations on the feature models and the products of the feature model. The tool is well documented and includes detailed information for each endpoint, making it easy to integrate the tool into the existing chatbot development workflow. By designing a systematic approach for chatbot development that emphasizes reuse, shared knowledge, and consistent user experiences, organizations could unlock the full potential of this technology. The concept of chatbot families could allow for improved scalability, efficiency, and a higher user experience.

¹<https://github.com/xatkit-bot-platform>

²<https://flamapy.github.io>

1.4. Document structure

The document structure of this Master's thesis project is organized as follows:

1. Chapter 1 is the introduction, which provides an overview of the problem and the motivation behind the research. It also presents contributions and research fields.
2. Chapter 2 is focused on project management, where we present the methodology used for the development of the project, the resources and tools used, as well as the schedule and risks associated with the project.
3. Chapter 3 presents a comprehensive literature review of existing approaches to chatbot development and software product line engineering. This chapter serves as a foundation for the proposed solution and the validation performed in the subsequent chapters.
4. Chapter 4 presents the proposed solution, which is the core contribution of this Master's thesis project. We explain in detail how the proposed tool leverages Software Product Line Engineering to optimize chatbot generation by reusing domain artifacts.
5. Chapter 5 provides a detailed overview of the technologies and frameworks that were used during the implementation phase of the project and focuses on the validation of the proposed solution. We discuss the results obtained from the evaluation of the proposed tool.
6. Chapter 6 discusses the conclusions of the research and provides some recommendations for future work in the area of chatbot development.
7. Appendices B and C contain additional information that complements the research, such as the material used for the validation, a guide to the proposed tool, and a glossary of technical terms used throughout the thesis.

2. Thesis project management

This chapter aims to provide an analysis of thesis project management. We will describe the methodology used and then discuss project time planning, including the resources required to complete it successfully.

2.1. Methodology

The research methodology used in this study was inspired by the work of Ida Solheim et al. on technology research [55]. This approach has been adapted to suit the specific nature of technology research, which aims to develop artifacts that surpass existing solutions in terms of factors such as speed, safety, or other technological characteristics. The primary objective is to demonstrate the completeness of these new artifacts, focusing on meeting the specified requirements rather than considering end-user perspectives. The methodology for technology research can be summarized into the following key steps:

- **Problem Statement:** This initial phase involves identifying potential needs for new technology or artifacts, emphasizing the identification of gaps in existing solutions.
- **Contribution:** In this phase, we focus on developing both the systematic approach and the solution and creating the necessary artifacts to support it.
- **Validation:** The final step involves verifying whether the requirements for improving previous solutions and addressing the identified problem have been met adequately.

Adhering to this research methodology, we formulated the abstract research question that guided our thesis: "Can chatbot generation be optimized through the reuse of domain-specific information?" To address this question, we followed a twofold process. First, we analyzed the existing variability within the problem space. Second, we proposed a systematic approach to address this variability and evaluated its effectiveness. To facilitate the evaluation, we developed a tool that leverages domain information in the field of chatbot generation.

2.2. Objectives

The general objective of this thesis project is to research on the field of chatbot development by exploring synergies with software product lines. The focus is on identifying the potential benefits and overcoming the limitations and challenges faced in current field of chatbot development, ultimately fostering the development of more efficient, scalable, and adaptable chatbot solutions through the integration of software product line techniques. The specific objectives that guide this research endeavor are as follows.

- Objective 1: Investigate existing approaches and techniques for chatbot generation and assess their limitations and challenges in using domain-specific information.
- Objective 2: Develop a systematic approach or methodology that incorporates domain-specific information into the chatbot generation process, with the aim of enhancing its efficiency, accuracy, or performance.
- Objective 3: Design and implement a prototype or tool that demonstrates the practical application of the proposed approach to generate domain-specific chatbots.

2.3. Time planning

The time planning for this project is based on effort points (EP), where 1 EP represents 1 hour of work. The estimated work for the project is 300 EP. 290 EP are allocated for tasks. The remaining 10 EP will be kept for flexibility in case any task requires additional time. Figure 2.1 shows the thesis time planning:

1. December:

- Task 1: Conduct a literature review on chatbot generation techniques and domain-specific information integration (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Task 2: Identify and analyze existing chatbot generation frameworks and tools (estimated duration: 10 effort points).
- Task 3: Define the specific objectives and research questions for the thesis project (estimated duration: 10 effort points).
- Milestone: Complete the literature review and finalize the research objectives.

2. January:

- Task 4: Design and develop a methodology to incorporate domain-specific information into chatbot generation (estimated duration: 30 effort points).
- Task 5: Identify and collect domain-specific data sets or resources for experimentation (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Milestone: Finalize the methodology and acquire the necessary domain-specific resources.

3. February:

- Task 6: Implement the proposed approach or tool for chatbot generation (estimated duration: 40 effort points).
- Task 7: Conduct iterative testing and refinement of the implemented solution (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Milestone: Complete the implementation and testing of the chatbot generation tool.

4. March:

- Task 8: Perform experiments and evaluations to compare the performance of the developed approach with existing methods (estimated duration: 30 effort points).
- Task 9: Analyze the experimental results and collect relevant performance metrics (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Milestone: Finish the experiments and gather data for analysis.

5. April:

- Task 10: Analyze and interpret the experimental results, comparing the performance of the developed approach with existing methods (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Task 11: Summarize the findings and draw conclusions from the analysis (estimated duration: 10 effort points).
- Task 12: Prepare the thesis write-up, including the methodology, results, discussion, and conclusion sections (estimated duration: 30 effort points).
- Milestone: Complete the analysis and begin writing the thesis.

6. May

- Task 13: Finalize the thesis statement, ensuring coherence, clarity, and proper reference (estimated duration: 20 effort points).
- Task 14: Proofread and revise grammar, spelling, and formatting (estimated duration: 10 effort points).
- Milestone: Submit the completed thesis for review and evaluation.

Figure 2.1: Thesis project gantt chart

2.4. Budget

Personnel Costs

- Junior Software Engineer: 2.000€ per month for 6 months
Total Personnel Costs: 12.000€

Equipment

- Laptop: 800€
- Software Licenses: 0€ (utilizing open-source or free software)

Contingency Fund

Allocate 10% of the total budget as a contingency fund. Assuming that the total budget is 12.800€ (Personnel Costs + Equipment Cost), the contingency fund would be 1.280€.

Total estimated

The funding needed for this project is 14.080€

Funding Sources

This research project is funded by the Regional Fund - COPERNICA Project:

- Reference: P20_01224
- Funding Program: PAIDI: Projects I+D+i
- Funding Entity: Consejería de Economía, Conocimiento, Empresas y Universidad

Part II

BACKGROUND

3. State of the art

3.1. Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the state-of-the-art in the field of software product lines and conversational interfaces, setting the foundation for the research presented in this master thesis. Software product lines have emerged as an approach to developing families of related software systems with varying features and functionalities. They enable systematic reuse of software artifacts, leading to increased productivity, improved quality, and reduced time-to-market.

Conversational interfaces, such as chatbots, have gained significant attention in recent years due to the proliferation of messaging platforms and the increasing demand for seamless human-computer interactions¹. Chatbots offer a way for users to interact with software systems, enabling them to obtain information, perform tasks, and engage in conversations. They have found applications in various domains, including customer support, e-commerce, healthcare, and more.

The intersection of software product lines and conversational interfaces presents an opportunity to take advantage of both approaches. By applying software product line techniques to the development of conversational interfaces, we can potentially achieve greater flexibility, modularity, and scalability in the design and implementation of chatbot-based systems. This research aims to explore this synergy and contribute to the advancement of both fields.

In the following sections, we will dive into the current state-of-the-art in software product lines, examining key concepts, techniques, and challenges. Subsequently, we will shift our focus to conversational interfaces, exploring the evolution of chatbot technologies, their underlying principles, and the existing research contributions. By understanding the existing landscape and identifying gaps, this chapter will lay the groundwork for subsequent chapters, in which we propose and evaluate an approach for developing conversational interfaces within the context of software product lines.

3.2. Software variability

Software variability, which refers to various features, configurations, and options within a software system, is a critical aspect to consider in modern software development [29]. Traditional one-size-fits-all solutions were no longer sufficient, as software must address diverse customer needs and deployment contexts, leading to challenges in software development, maintenance, and evolution [18]. In this context, software product lines emerge as a valuable approach to effectively manage and evolve variant-rich software systems. By adopting a family-oriented perspective, software product lines focus on systematically addressing software variability by identifying and reusing commonal-

¹<https://www.gartner.com/en/newsroom/press-releases/2022-07-27-gartner-predicts-chatbots-will-become-a-primary-customer-service-channel-within-five-years>

ities and variability across a family of related software systems [5]. This approach enables the development and maintenance of variant-rich software in a more efficient and consistent manner, as it explicitly represents the shared characteristics and unique variations within the product line. We no longer think of producing a product for a single customer. From the subroutines of the 1960s, through modular and object-oriented programming languages to frameworks and SPL's, we have arrived at the need to build software that allows one to build software that allows a high level of customization. This can be seen in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: SPLE evolution and development in [10]

Managing software variability within a product line is a significant challenge that requires accurately mapping and representing the commonalities and variability of the software system [46]. This mapping is crucial for systematic reuse, efficient development, and consistent maintenance of various product variants within the product line. Software product lines provide methods and tools to model and manage software variability. Feature models, for example, offer a structured approach to identify and present commonalities and variability within the product line [34]. By visualizing features and their relationships, feature models help to understand variant space and facilitate decision making during product configuration. This systematic representation of variability enables adaptation to changing customer needs, reduces development efforts, and improves overall product quality. Additionally, systematic testing, maintenance, and evolution of the software product line are made possible by explicit representation of variability, which increases overall effectiveness and efficiency [32].

3.2.1 Software product lines

Software product line engineering emphasizes the creation of a family of software products based on shared features rather than building each one from scratch in order to achieve greater customization. This fundamental change is essential because it allows greater efficiency and customization compared to the production of individual systems. These techniques focus on creating a variety of similar systems. Organizations can successfully address the problems posed by the information systems market by offering customized solutions to satisfy their customers' various needs and preferences.

This strategy improves market competitiveness by enabling more effective development processes, the reuse of shared components, rapid adaptation to changing customer demands, and the creation of mass-produced custom products.

According to Tseng and Jiao [59], mass customization is the process of effectively producing goods and services that meet the needs of specific customers while preserving the benefits of mass production. In this definition, two crucial elements are highlighted. First and foremost, mass customization aims to meet a variety of unique customer needs, including the various features of modern mobile phones. Second, it aims to be as efficient as mass production at high levels. Practitioners suggest utilizing existing resources that have more in common than distinct characteristics when building products to achieve this efficiency. Compared to more conventional branches of the industry, the information systems market stands out as a distinct sector. Information systems' development can be viewed as a progression from artisan methods to mass production and now towards mass customization to thrive in the market by drawing comparisons to the history of traditional industries. The idea of mass customization for software products is frequently referred to as "software product lines" [21] or "software product families". [50]

There exist some differences between how the customization works in software product lines. For this explanation, we have defined two different approaches shown in Figure 3.2. The traditional approach is defined by the construction of products without a marked line of those that are common to both. However, it is difficult to reuse components because they are tightly coupled to the product specificity. SPL proposes to extract the common parts of the products into what are called core assets. These assets, together with the rest of the features of all products, are modeled through a feature model.

Figure 3.2: Differences between the traditional and SPL approach

In many different areas of software production, such as embedded systems for mobile devices, embedded software for cars, and avionics, software product lines have seen significant growth [60]. Several problems arise when a company decides to build its own software product line. They must address issues like how to specify the software

product line itself and a specific product within it. At first, there was a ton of evidence to suggest that defining product lines based on their features could be an answer. Other industries often define product lines based on their features. Products in a software product line are distinguished by their unique features, each of which represents an incremental improvement in the functionality of the program [9]. As a result, feature models are used to specify software product lines, whereas individual products are specified using features.

3.2.2 Feature models

Kang et al. coined the term "feature model" in the 1990 FODA report [34]. Since then, the study of feature models has received a lot of attention in the software product line industry. To represent and control feature models, several feature model languages have been created. A feature model represents the data pertaining to all potential products within a software product line, outlining their characteristics and interrelationships. An example is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: An example of a feature model shown in [12]

In the field of software product line engineering, it is a widely used information model. Two main elements make up a feature model's hierarchical arrangement of features:

1. Relationships between the characteristics: The makeup and order of the product line's features are determined by these relationships.
2. Cross-tree constraints: These constraints specify dependencies between features, such as whether features A and B must be included or excluded if feature F is included.

Software product line engineers can effectively capture feature variability and relationships by using a feature model, allowing for the systematic and configurable development of product lines. A variety of relationships between features, such as mandatory, optional, alternative, and or-relationships, are included in basic feature models. Within a feature model, these relationships describe the dependencies and limitations of the characteristics of parents and children [12]. An overview of each type of relationship is provided below.

1. **Mandatory:** All features where the parent feature appears must include the child because they have a mandatory relationship with their parent. For example, every mobile phone system must support calls.
2. **Optional:** A child feature can be included or excluded from products where the parent feature is present because of an optional relationship with that feature. Software for mobile phones may optionally support GPS in the example of a mobile phone.
3. **Alternative:** Only one feature from a set of child features can be chosen when the parent feature is present in the product because they have an alternative relationship with their parent. Mobile phones, for instance, may support a basic, color, or high-resolution screen, but only one of these is available.
4. **Or:** one or more features from the set can be chosen because they have an or-relationship with their parent. In the example, you can choose either "Camera," MP3, or both whenever the "Media" feature is selected.

It is crucial to keep in mind that a product can only have features for children if the parent feature is also present. All products in the software product line share the root feature. Cross-tree constraints, such as "requires" and "excludes" relationships, can also be included in feature models.

1. **Requires:** Inclusion of feature B in a product implies that feature A must be present if necessary. For example, high-resolution screen support is required for mobile phones with cameras.
2. **Excludes:** If feature A excludes feature B, both features cannot be part of the same product. The incompatibility between features is illustrated by the example of a basic screen and GPS.

More complex cross-tree relationships, allowing for generic propositional formulas (e.g., "A and B implies not C"), have been proposed in later literature to express additional constraints between features [8]. These expanded relationships offer greater flexibility and expressive power in capturing dependencies within feature models.

Feature models are used in a variety of software production scenarios, including those centered on the development of software product lines, such as model-driven development [58], feature-oriented programming [7], software factories [30], and generative programming [22]. This emphasizes how crucial feature models are to the field of information systems. Information systems professionals can capture and represent the variability and relationships between features in various aspects of software development and system design by utilizing feature models, allowing for more methodical and flexible approaches to software engineering.

3.2.3 Existing tools

In the field of software product lines, the community has proposed multiple techniques for automated model analysis [28], as well as specific languages for their representation, such as the Universal Variability Language (UVL) [25]. UVL is a domain-specific

language [26] used to represent and manage variability. This language provides a way to express the variability and commonalities within a product line.

Automated analysis of feature models (AAFMs) involves extracting relevant information from feature models using algorithms. This information is then used by product line engineers to improve their strategies and make informed decisions. In [27], various analysis operations on feature models were reported along with an AAFM based tool, FLAMA which is a framework for modeling and analysis of different sets of models, including feature models. These operations provide insight into the capabilities offered by automated analysis tools, such as model validity check and error detection.

In addition, various tools have been developed for automated analysis of software product lines, including FaMa [11] and FeatureIDE [36], among others. These tools and operations enable software product line engineers to gain valuable insights, validate product configurations, and identify potential errors or inconsistencies in their feature models. They play a crucial role in ensuring the effectiveness and reliability of software product lines. Specifically, FeatureIDE is an Eclipse-based IDE that supports all phases of feature-oriented software development for the development of software product lines: domain analysis, domain design, domain implementation, and requirements analysis [3]. Integrates different SPL implementation techniques such as feature-oriented programming (FOP) and aspect-oriented programming (AOP) [37].

Pure::Variants [14] is one of the few commercial tools specifically designed for the development of product lines. It covers the entire spectrum of product line development, from product line design to product generation. With Pure::Variants, the development of the product line is divided into two steps. The first step involves analyzing the problem domain and solution space, identifying and applying general domain engineering procedures. In the second step, individual products are derived from the product line through application engineering processes [15].

3.3. Conversational interfaces

Conversational interfaces [43] represent a significant advancement in human-computer interaction, allowing users to interact with computer systems using natural language conversations. These interfaces, which cover various forms such as chatbots, virtual assistants, and voice-based systems, aim to create seamless and intuitive interactions between humans and machines. They have gained popularity across different domains and platforms, ranging from messaging apps and websites to smart devices and virtual environments. They are used in various applications, such as customer support, information retrieval, task automation, entertainment, etc. [63]. By simulating human-like conversations, these interfaces bridge the gap between users and technology, enabling users to interact with systems in a more conversational and intuitive manner. As it is sometimes misunderstood, its important to first state the differences between conversational interfaces and chatbots:

A conversational interface refers to the interaction between a user and a computer system using natural language. It allows users to communicate with the system through text or speech, simulating a conversation-like experience. Conversational interfaces can

be found in various applications, such as voice assistants, messaging apps, customer support systems, and more. A chatbot is a specific type of conversational interface designed to automate conversations with users. It is a software application that uses artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, including natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning, to understand user input and provide relevant responses. Chatbots can be deployed on various platforms, including websites, messaging apps, and voice-enabled devices.

The technologies and techniques that power conversational interfaces are vast. Natural language understanding (NLU) [4] allows systems to comprehend and extract meaning from user input, while natural language generation (NLG) [42] enables systems to produce human-like responses. Machine learning algorithms and deep learning models play a crucial role in training chatbots and virtual assistants to improve their performance over time.

Unlike traditional graphical user interfaces (GUIs), which rely on menus, buttons, and forms, chatbots take advantage of natural language processing (NLP) and artificial intelligence (AI) to understand user inputs, interpret intentions, and provide appropriate responses [35]. This paradigm shift offers several benefits, including increased accessibility, ease of use, and a more personalized user experience. Chatbots also rely on various components to facilitate interaction, such as dialog management systems, context tracking mechanisms, and integration with back-end systems or databases to retrieve relevant information. In addition, they often incorporate visual elements, such as cards, buttons, and rich media, to enhance conversation and provide a more engaging experience.

As chatbots continue to evolve, there are ongoing research and development efforts to improve their capabilities. These include advancements in language understanding, dialogue modeling, multimodal interactions (combining text, voice, and visuals) and personalized user experiences. Furthermore, the integration of conversational interfaces with emerging technologies such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) opens up new possibilities for immersive and interactive conversational experiences [57].

3.3.1 Chatbots

Chatbots, also known as chatterbots or conversational agents, are AI-powered systems designed to engage in conversations with humans through textual or auditory means. These intelligent virtual assistants simulate human-like interactions and provide automated responses to user queries or requests [51]. Chatbots have gained significant popularity in recent years, finding applications in customer service, information retrieval, personal assistance, and various other domains [2].

Chatbots often employ machine learning algorithms and AI models to enhance their capabilities [31]. They can be trained using supervised learning techniques on large datasets of conversations to improve their understanding and response generation. Reinforcement learning and deep learning models, such as recurrent neural networks (RNN) or transformer models such as GPT (Generative Pretrained Transformer), have also been proven to be effective in chatbot development [44]. To provide accurate and up-to-date information, chatbots are often integrated with back-end sys-

tems or databases. This integration allows chatbots to access relevant data or perform actions based on user requests. For example, a customer service chatbot might retrieve information from a knowledge base or connect to a booking system to schedule appointments. There are several types of chatbot depending on their functionalities and underlying technologies. Here are some common types of chatbots based on [1]:

- **Rule-Based Chatbots:** Rule-based chatbots follow predefined sets of rules and patterns to respond to user input. These rules are typically created and maintained by human developers. Rule-based chatbots are suitable for scenarios with specific, well-defined tasks and limited conversational complexity. They rely on keyword matching or pattern recognition to determine the appropriate responses.
- **Retrieval-Based Chatbots:** Retrieval-based chatbots use predefined responses from a database or knowledge base to generate replies. They analyze user input, match it with preexisting responses, and select the most appropriate one based on similarity metrics or machine learning techniques. Retrieval-based chatbots are effective in providing specific and concise answers but may struggle in handling complex or out-of-context queries.
- **Generative Chatbots:** Generative chatbots are powered by natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning techniques. They generate responses based on an understanding of the input context and can produce more diverse and contextually relevant responses. Generative chatbots often utilize deep learning models, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) or transformer models, to generate human-like responses. These chatbots can handle a wider range of queries, but may occasionally produce inaccurate responses.
- **Hybrid Chatbots:** Hybrid chatbots combine the features of rule-based and generative chatbots. They use a rule-based approach for predefined tasks and simple queries while employing generative techniques for handling more complex or ambiguous conversations. Hybrid chatbots provide a balance between flexibility and control, leveraging rule-based systems for accuracy and generative models for creativity.

Chatbots operate through a series of internal processes to facilitate conversational interactions with users. When a user initiates a conversation, their input is first processed by the Natural Language Understanding (NLU) component, which interprets the user's message, extracting important information such as intent and entities. The Dialog State Tracking system then maintains the conversation context and informs the Dialog Manager of the extracted intent and entities. The Dialog Manager, using the current state of the conversation, determines the appropriate action to take, such as querying a knowledge database for relevant information. A Dialog Policy guides the chatbot's behavior, ensuring appropriate responses and filtering out potential risks. Finally, the Natural Language Generation (NLG) component formulates a response based on the output from the Dialog Manager, providing a human-like reply to the user's query. In Figure 3.4 we can see an example interaction between a user and a chatbot.

Figure 3.4: Chatbot interaction overview in [59]

Imagine a user asking the chatbot: "I want to find a Chinese restaurant." We will walk through each step of the chatbot's internal workings, from the NLU understanding the user's intent and extracting the cuisine type to the Dialog Manager triggering a query in the knowledge database. The chatbot's response will be generated using the NLG engine, offering a suitable suggestion to the user's query:

1. User input: Conversation begins when the user interacts with the chatbot by sending a message or asking a question. For example, the user might ask, "I want to find a Chinese restaurant."
2. Natural Language Understanding (NLU): The user's input is passed through the NLU component, which analyzes and interprets the user's message. Extracts important information such as the user's intent (finding a restaurant) and entities (cuisine type: Chinese).
3. Dialog State Tracking: The dialog state tracking system keeps track of the conversation's context and maintains the state of the conversation. Updates the dialog manager with the extracted intent and entities from the user's input.
4. Dialog Manager: The dialog manager processes the current dialog state and decides how to respond. Determines the appropriate action or query to be performed based on the user's intent and the current state of the conversation. In this case, it may trigger a query to the knowledge database to find Chinese restaurants.
5. Knowledge Database: The chatbot's knowledge database contains relevant information, such as restaurant listings or recommendations. The dialog manager queries the database to retrieve the desired information based on the user's request.
6. Dialog policy: The dialog policy serves as a set of rules or guidelines that dictate the chatbot's behavior and response selection. It helps filter out potentially dangerous or inappropriate interactions to ensure a safe and appropriate conversation.
7. Natural Language Generation (NLG): The NLG component generates a natural language response based on the output of the dialog manager. It formulates a

response that is relevant to the user’s query and conveys the information effectively. For example, the chatbot might respond with ”We have several Chinese restaurants available. Where would you like to eat?”

3.3.2 Natural language processing

NLP, or Natural Language Processing, can be divided into three main components [53]: NLU (Natural Language Understanding), NER (Named Entity Recognition), and NLG (Natural Language Generation). A table resuming the main concepts is shown in 3.1.

Component	Function	Application
NLU	Extracts meaning and intent from text	Understand user inputs
NER	Identifies and classifies entities	Information extraction
NLG	Generates human-like text	Generating responses

Table 3.1: NLP main components and their application

Natural language understanding (NLU)

NLU focuses on extracting meaning and intent from inputs of natural language [13]. It involves techniques such as tokenization, sentence splitting, part-of-speech tagging, and syntactic parsing. NLU helps to understand the structure and semantics of the input text. It enables systems to recognize user intents, extract key information, and determine appropriate actions or responses.

Named entity recognition (NER)

NER is a specific task within NLP that aims to identify and classify named entities in text [41]. Named entities can include names of people, organizations, locations, dates, and more. NER techniques use machine learning models or rule-based approaches to recognize and categorize named entities. It helps to extract specific information from text, which is crucial for various applications such as information retrieval, question-response, and knowledge extraction.

Natural language generation (NLG)

NLG focuses on generating human-like text or speech as output based on given data or instructions [24]. It involves techniques such as text planning, sentence structuring, lexical choice, and surface realization. NLG systems can generate coherent and contextually appropriate responses or narratives. NLG is often used in chatbots, virtual assistants, and other applications where generating human-readable text is necessary.

Most relevant processes

In Figure 3.5, we can observe an example of an NLP pipeline implemented by Linguamatics², a well-known provider of NLP solutions. The pipeline showcases how

²<https://www.linguamatics.com/>

various NLP steps, such as tokenization, sentence splitting, part-of-speech tagging, named entity recognition (NER), and syntactic parsing, are orchestrated to process natural language text. This NLP pipeline illustrates the sequential flow of tasks involved in understanding and extracting meaningful information from text data. Each step contributes to the overall comprehension of the text, enabling subsequent analysis or generating insights. Linguamatics' NLP pipeline serves as a representation of the complex processes involved in natural language understanding and showcases the integration of different NLP components for effective text processing and analysis.

Figure 3.5: Most relevant NLP processes in [60]

Tokenization Tokenization [62] is the process of breaking down the text into individual words or tokens. It involves splitting the text based on whitespace or punctuation marks to create meaningful units for further analysis. For example, the sentence "I love ice cream" would be tokenized into the following tokens: ["I", "love", "ice", "cream"].

Sentence splitting Sentence splitting [56] involves identifying the boundaries between sentences within a text. This process helps segment the text into individual sentences, enabling further analysis at the sentence level. For example, the paragraph "I love ice cream. It is my favorite dessert." would be split into the following sentences: ["I love ice cream.", "It is my favorite dessert."]

Part-of-speech tagging Part-of-Speech (POS) [61] tagging involves assigning grammatical labels or tags to each word in a sentence, indicating its syntactic category or function. Common POS tags include nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, etc. For example, in the sentence "I love ice cream", the POS tags would be: ["pronoun", "verb", "noun", "noun"].

Chunking Chunking [38], also known as shallow parsing, involves grouping words into meaningful chunks or phrases based on their POS tags. It helps to identify phrases such as noun phrases, verb phrases, or prepositional phrases. For example, in the sentence "I love ice cream", the noun phrase chunk would be "ice cream".

Querying and class matching After the initial preprocessing steps, the processed text can be queried against a predefined set of classes or categories. This involves matching [39] the extracted information with the available classes or patterns to identify relevant categories. For example, if the text mentions "Chinese restaurant," it can be matched with a class or category related to restaurants specializing in Chinese cuisine.

3.3.3 Existing tools

Several tools provide comprehensive frameworks and platforms for building, training, and deploying chatbots. These tools offer various features such as natural language processing, dialogue management, integration with messaging channels, and analytics. Some popular chatbot development tools include:

- **ChatGPT:** ChatGPT³, developed by OpenAI, is an advanced conversational AI model capable of generating human-like responses in chat-based interactions. It uses deep learning techniques to understand and generate text in a conversational context.
- **Dialogflow:** Developed by Google, Dialogflow⁴ offers a cloud-based platform for building conversational interfaces. It provides natural language understanding (NLU) capabilities, pre-built agents, and integration with popular messaging platforms.
- **IBM Watson Assistant:** IBM Watson Assistant⁵ is an AI-powered chatbot development platform that allows companies to create conversational agents for different use cases. It offers NLU, dialogue management, and integration with various channels.
- **Microsoft Bot Framework:** The Microsoft Bot Framework⁶ enables developers to build and deploy chatbots across multiple channels, including web, mobile, and messaging platforms. It provides NLU capabilities, dialog management, and integration with Azure services.
- **Xatkit:** Xatkit⁷ is an open source chatbot development platform that allows developers to create and deploy chatbots across multiple channels. It provides customizable NLU, dialog management, and integration capabilities.
- **Rasa:** Rasa⁸ is an open-source framework for building AI-powered chatbots. It offers tools and libraries for NLU, dialogue management, and customizing chatbot behavior. Rasa provides flexibility for developers to design highly customizable conversational agents.

These tools, among others, provide developers with the necessary features and functionalities to create sophisticated and interactive chatbot applications.

³<https://chat.openai.com/>

⁴<https://cloud.google.com/dialogflow>

⁵<https://www.ibm.com/products/watson-assistant>

⁶<https://dev.botframework.com/>

⁷<https://xatkit.com/>

⁸<https://rasa.com/>

3.4. Relevant findings

In the field of chatbot development, there are tools available that allow semi-automated or fully automated bot generation, such as DialogFlow or Xatkit. Many existing tools have already addressed this problem. Additionally, research has explored this topic extensively.

- In [19], the history of conversational interfaces, particularly chatbots, is narrated. The fundamental components of a chatbot are discussed, and proprietary tools like DialogFlow, which automate chatbot creation, are introduced
- In [40], a chatbot is proposed that provides answers based on databases or FAQ pages, similar to one of the functionality of DialogFlow.
- In [20], a proposal is described to create bots using HTML tags.

Additionally, we have come across information that may not be directly relevant to this Master's thesis but could be of interest in the future:

- In [54], an architecture is proposed to detect emotions in user inputs and respond based on those inputs.
- In [33], an architecture is proposed to test the effectiveness of a chatbot by asking questions, along with mentioning some best practices for creating these questions.
- In [17], a chatbot is proposed to configure a product line, which is the opposite of what we propose in our thesis.
- In [47], an experiment is conducted where a bot responds to StackOverflow questions, first using a human name and then identifying itself as a bot. The experiment showed that users were more likely to accept responses from the bot when it identified itself as a person.

However, there is no current solution to reuse the information that a company already has to create bots. If we had to create multiple chatbots that may share common information, we would have to generate them one by one. For instance, if we wanted to create a chatbot for all universities in Andalusia, Spain, even though the universities may have a lot of common information or components, we would still have to build them individually. This becomes problematic because companies would end up with chatbots having completely different structures. One straightforward way to reuse information within a domain when generating chatbots is to apply product line techniques. Although there is limited information specifically applied to chatbots, we did come across a proposal that utilizes product line techniques for generating generic bots:

- In [23], a solution is proposed to address a chatbot product line from a different perspective. The product line creates generic bots that need to be contextualized.

In the context of developing chatbots, a fundamental question arises: Can we move beyond simply defining the structure of a chatbot and tackle the challenge of populating it with meaningful content? This question serves as a starting point for further exploration in the scope of this master's thesis. The underlying issue lies in existing tools, which often provide empty templates despite their ability to generate

bots. As a result, the process of filling chatbots with relevant information, defining intents, and configuring responses becomes laborious and time consuming. Although these tools offer preassembled "boxes" that eliminate the need to set up NLP servers or deployment infrastructure, the resulting chatbots lack substantial content.

Furthermore, the challenge of reusing information between multiple chatbots persists, necessitating manual efforts to add content each time. The current approach involves individually defining and updating each chatbot, leading to a potentially chaotic process. Additionally, maintaining consistency and providing support for multiple chatbots becomes increasingly challenging as the information evolves and differs between various instances. To illustrate, consider a restaurant company with multiple establishments in the city. Although there are certain components shared between all restaurants, such as the menu, opening hours, and policies, there are also differences, including unique dishes and variations of the facilities. Under the current approach, developing a chatbot for each restaurant would involve gathering company information from various sources, such as documents, databases, or cloud providers. These data would then need to be preprocessed and separate chatbot instances would be created using the aforementioned tools. Each chatbot would be trained with the specific data of its corresponding restaurant and subsequently deployed on the Web. Given the similarities and differences among the chatbots, this process would have to be repeated for each restaurant, resulting in the creation of custom-made ad hoc chatbots.

3.5. Summary

In this chapter, we conducted a state-of-the-art analysis of two interrelated fields: chatbots and software product lines. Our exploration delved into complex and advanced concepts, examining the fundamental principles, architectures, and components of conversational interfaces. We explore various types of chatbot, their functionalities, and the underlying technologies that drive their interactions.

Furthermore, we investigated the potential synergies between chatbot development and software product lines, recognizing the potential for leveraging software product line techniques to optimize chatbot generation and reuse domain-specific information. By applying product line engineering principles, we can address the challenges of creating and maintaining multiple chatbots, enabling efficient knowledge reuse and facilitating consistent responses across different instances.

Our review of the literature involved an exploration of existing research and commercial tools. We scrutinized the current state-of-the-art, identifying gaps and areas within the field of chatbot development. On the basis of the insights gained from our study, we are now ready to dive deeper into the identified prob. By proposing an approach for mass production of custom chatbots, we aim to optimize the creation and reusability of chatbots, leveraging domain-specific information to generate contextually relevant and intelligent conversational agents. The findings and contributions of this research have the potential to advance the field of chatbot development, enhancing their capabilities and effectiveness in various domains.

Part III
PROPOSAL

4. Proposal description

4.1. Introduction

Existing approaches to chatbot generation and information reuse face several challenges and limitations. While tools and frameworks are available to automate chatbot creation, they often result in empty or generic bots that lack the necessary domain-specific knowledge. This leads to a significant manual effort to populate the chatbots with relevant information, define intentions, and ensure the coherence and accuracy of responses.

Furthermore, current methods do not adequately address the problem of reusing information across multiple chatbots. Each chatbot is typically created individually, which results in redundant efforts to define and maintain similar content across different instances. This approach is not only time-consuming but also prone to inconsistencies and difficulties in keeping the chatbots up-to-date with evolving information.

The lack of a systematic approach to generating chatbots and reusing information within a specific domain hinders the scalability and efficiency of chatbot development processes. Organizations that require multiple chatbots, such as government agencies, educational institutions, or large enterprises, face the challenge of creating and managing chatbots individually, even when they share common information or components.

In the literature, limited research has been conducted specifically to address these challenges. While some studies propose generic chatbot frameworks or focus on isolated aspects of chatbot generation, there is a notable gap in addressing the systematic reusability of information within a specific domain for efficient chatbot creation.

Therefore, there is a clear need for a solution that enables the effective generation of chatbots by leveraging domain-specific information and facilitates the reusability of knowledge across multiple instances. By addressing this problem, our goal is to streamline the chatbot development process, improve efficiency, and ensure consistent and accurate responses across different chatbot instances. In the following sections, we present our proposed approach that addresses these challenges and provides a tool for generating domain-specific and contextually aware chatbots.

4.2. Proposal overview

The proposed approach consists of several key processes that aim to simplify the development and deployment of chatbots.

- **Preprocessing:** To maintain consistency and ensure structured data input, the initial step involves preprocessing of the information provided by the users. This preprocessing step ensures that the data is organized and structured in a way that facilitates further processing.

- Featurization [49]: After preprocessing, the next step is to featurize the information. Featurization involves creating a feature model that represents the variability of the information. This feature model serves as the foundation for the chatbot product line, where each feature corresponds to a specific aspect of the company or domain.
- Chatbot product line generation [48]: The chatbot product line serves as a centralized repository of information, making it easy to generate customized chatbots without the need to preprocess the information every time.
- Configuration [52]: Users can select which features they want to incorporate into their chatbot, essentially configuring the chatbot to meet their specific requirements.
- Deployment: Once the configuration process is completed, the chatbot is ready for deployment. The deployment process involves making the chatbot available on the Web or other desired platforms.

By leveraging the chatbot product line, creating additional chatbots becomes a streamlined process of selecting the desired features and configuring the chatbot accordingly. This approach allows multiple chatbots to be created within the same domain, ensuring customization for each specific restaurant or entity. Now, let us consider a scenario where we aim to create chatbots for different restaurants within a city. While each restaurant has its own unique characteristics, there are commonalities and differences that can be addressed using the proposed solution. One common feature among restaurants is their opening hours and closing times. Another common feature is the menu. Most restaurants have menus that include various dishes, drinks, and specials. However, restaurants may have different facilities or amenities available. For example, some restaurants may have outdoor seating areas, while others may have private dining rooms or lounges. Following the proposal in Figure 4.1, with our approach, we would perform the following processes:

Figure 4.1: Our chatbot generation proposal

- **Preprocessing:** Gather the necessary information from each restaurant, such as opening hours, closing times, menu items, facilities, specialties, and any other relevant details.
- **Featurization:** Create a feature model that captures the variability in the information obtained from the restaurants. Identify common features, such as opening hours and menu items, as well as unique features, such as facilities and specialties, for each restaurant.
- **Chatbot product line generation:** Utilize the feature model as a foundation for generating a chatbot product line. The chatbot product line will serve as a repository of reusable components and configurations. Each feature within the product line corresponds to a specific aspect of the restaurant, allowing for customization.
- **Configuration:** Users can select the desired features from the chatbot product line to configure their chatbot. For example, they can choose the opening hours and menu features that are applicable to their restaurant. They can also enable or disable features based on the facilities available or unique specialties offered. This configuration process allows users to tailor the chatbot to their specific restaurant.
- **Deployment:** Once the configuration is complete, the chatbot is ready for deployment. Deploy the chatbot on the desired platforms, such as websites, messaging apps, or voice assistants. The chatbot will incorporate the selected features and be capable of providing relevant and customized information based on the configuration.

4.3. Chatbot SPL definition

In this section, we provide an overview of the proposed approach for the chatbot product line, which aims to enable the efficient generation of contextually aware and domain-specific chatbots by leveraging reusable assets. The approach follows the two main processes of product line engineering: application engineering and domain engineering.

For this master thesis, we will simplify the complexity of the chatbot product line and focus on the reuse of intents. Intents represent the specific goals or actions that users express when interacting with a chatbot. By reusing intents, we can ensure consistent behavior and responses across different chatbot instances within the product line. With the variability-related model defined, we can derive products from the configured product line by selecting and configuring the desired intents. This approach enables the generation of specialized chatbot products tailored to specific user requirements while minimizing the effort required for development and maintenance.

The domain engineering process focuses on the expertise of the product line expert in charge of defining the chatbot product line. This expert has deep knowledge of the chatbot domain and understands the specific characteristics and requirements of the target users. By combining this expertise with the identified reusable assets, the domain engineering process maps these assets into a feature model representation. The feature model captures the variability within the chatbot product line and serves as a blueprint

for deriving individual chatbot products. In our context, a feature model of intents is defined, where each feature in the model represents a set of intents.

On the other hand, the application engineering process involves the analysis of product requirements. It encompasses the gathering of customer needs, user feedback, and market trends to identify the desired features and functionalities of chatbot products. By understanding the requirements, we gain insights into the variations and commonalities among the chatbot products within the product line. This process allows us to define an overview of the products that will be generated and to identify reusable assets that can be leveraged. Here, we have the task of selecting and configuring the desired intents from the feature model. This selection process allows the customization and adaptation of chatbots based on specific user requirements. Once the selection is made, the configuration process generates the chatbot product, incorporating the relevant information associated with the selected intents. This includes training data, response templates, and any other necessary resources.

The approach proposed in Figure 4.2 provides a systematic way of generating chatbot products and reusing domain-specific assets. This could lead to greater efficiency, consistency, and scalability in chatbot development processes. It is important to point out that this SPL proposal is independent of the underlying technologies used to implement it.

Figure 4.2: Chatbot SPL definition

4.4. Processes description

In this section, we provide an overview of the key processes involved in our proposed chatbot development approach. We go into the details of each process, highlighting

their objectives, activities, and the role of our proof-of-concept tool in facilitating their execution.

Data preprocessing

In this process, the focus is on preparing the data in a structured and consistent manner to ensure its suitability for the generation of chatbots. Users are required to input the information in a predefined format to maintain consistency across different chatbots. The data preprocessing step involves cleaning the data, resolving inconsistencies, and standardizing the format. This ensures that subsequent processes can run smoothly on the processed data. Preprocessing also includes data validation and verification to minimize errors and inaccuracies in the information being utilized. For the data preprocessing process, the proof-of-concept tool we will develop should provide functionalities to facilitate the following tasks.

- **Data cleaning:** The tool should have the ability to clean the input data by removing irrelevant or unnecessary information, correcting misspellings or typos, and handling special characters or formatting issues. This ensures that the data is in a clean and consistent state for further processing.
- **Inconsistency resolution:** The tool should assist in identifying and resolving inconsistencies within the data. This could involve handling variations in terminology, reconciling conflicting information, and ensuring uniformity across different sources or input formats.
- **Format standardization:** To ensure compatibility and consistency, the tool should support standardizing the format of the data. This may involve converting data from different sources into a common format, applying data transformation techniques, and organizing the data in a structured manner.
- **Data validation and verification:** The tool should provide mechanisms to validate the processed data, ensuring its integrity and accuracy. This could include performing data quality checks, verifying data against predefined rules or constraints, and identifying potential errors or discrepancies for manual review.
- **User interface for data input:** To maintain consistency across different chatbots, the tool should provide a user-friendly interface for users to input the required data in a predefined format. The interface should guide users to provide the necessary information and to provide a prompt for missing or incomplete data.

Feature modeling

Featurization is a critical step that involves capturing the variability in the information and representing it in the form of a feature model. The feature model serves as a blueprint for the chatbot product line, where each feature corresponds to a specific aspect or component of the chatbot. In our restaurant example, features can include menu items, opening hours, policies, unique dishes, or any other relevant information for the domain. The feature model allows for systematic organization and representation of information, enabling easy configuration and customization of chatbots based on the desired features. In the Featurization process, the proof-of-concept tool will

provide support for users to create and validate their feature model using the standard language for variability, UVL. The tool shall offer the following functionalities:

- **Validity checking:** The tool will perform validation checks to ensure that the user-defined feature model is syntactically and semantically correct according to the UVL language specifications. It will highlight any errors or inconsistencies in the model and provide feedback to the user for corrections.
- **Feature-information mapping:** The tool will associate each feature of the model with the corresponding information obtained from the data preprocessing process. This could involve linking features to specific attributes, files, or databases where the relevant information is stored.
- **Integration of information input:** The tool will provide a mechanism for users to input the required information for each feature in the feature model. This could be done through an interface that allows users to upload data files, enter text-based information, or connect to external data sources.

Chatbot product line generation

Once the feature model is established, the generation process becomes straightforward. The chatbot product line is created, consisting of a collection of features representing the available information within the domain. These features serve as the building blocks for chatbot configuration. The product line generation involves defining the relationships and dependencies between features, ensuring the consistency and coherence of the chatbot product line. This step establishes a unified framework from which different chatbots can be derived and configured. In the Chatbot product line generation process, the proof-of-concept tool will provide support for users to generate the chatbot product line based on the defined feature model. The tool shall offer the following functionalities:

- **Dependency management:** The tool will manage the dependencies between features, ensuring that any required dependencies are properly resolved during the product line generation. It will analyze the relationships defined in the feature model and provide feedback to users in case of any conflicts or inconsistencies.
- **Configuration options:** The tool will provide an interface for configuring the chatbot product line. Users can specify the values or settings for each feature, tailoring the chatbots to their specific requirements. The tool will enforce constraints and validate the configurations based on the defined feature dependencies.
- **Product line validation:** The tool will perform validation checks on the generated chatbot product line to ensure its integrity and consistency. It will verify that all the selected features are compatible and that the configured options are valid within the defined constraints. Any inconsistencies or errors will be highlighted, allowing users to make the necessary adjustments.

Chatbot configuration

The chatbot configuration process involves selecting the desired features from the chatbot product line to create a specific instance of a chatbot. With the feature model as a reference, users can choose the relevant features that align with the user requirements. This configuration step allows for the customization and adaptation of chatbots while leveraging the shared features and information stored in the chatbot product line. The configuration process ensures that each chatbot is tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of the restaurant, while maintaining consistency in terms of the underlying structure and shared information. In the chatbot configuration process, the proof-of-concept tool will facilitate the creation of custom chatbots by providing the following functionalities:

- **Configuration interface:** The tool will offer an interface where users can configure their chatbot by selecting the desired features from the feature model. The interface will display the available features and allow users to choose which ones to include in their chatbot instance.
- **Validity checking:** The tool will perform validity checks on the user's configuration to ensure that it aligns with the constraints and dependencies specified in the feature model. It will verify that the selected features are compatible and satisfy any restrictions or rules defined in the model.
- **Automatic data loading:** Based on the user's configuration, the tool will automatically load the corresponding information associated with the selected features from the data preprocessing step. It will retrieve the relevant data attributes, files, or database entries and integrate them into the chatbot.
- **Chatbot training:** Once the configuration is validated and the necessary data is loaded, the tool will automatically train the chatbot using the selected information. It will utilize machine learning algorithms or natural language processing techniques to enable the chatbot to understand and respond to user queries effectively.
- **Automatic compilation:** The tool will compile the chatbot, ensuring that all necessary components, dependencies, and configurations are properly integrated. This compilation process will result in a self-contained chatbot package that is ready for deployment.

Deployment and reusability

Once the chatbot is configured with the desired features, it is ready for deployment. The deployment process involves making the chatbot accessible to users, typically through a web interface. The tool will offer the following capabilities:

- **Web Integration:** The tool will facilitate the deployment of the chatbot by providing options to integrate it with a web interface or popular messaging platforms. This will allow users to interact with the chatbot conveniently through an interface.
- **Downloadable chatbot:** To ensure flexibility and allow users to have full control

over their chatbots, the tool will provide the ability to download the chatbot. Users can download the compiled chatbot, which includes all the necessary files, configurations, and dependencies, and deploy it on their own servers or hosting platforms according to their requirements.

- Documentation and support: The tool will provide documentation and support resources to guide users through the deployment process. It will offer step-by-step instructions, configuration guidelines, and troubleshooting tips to facilitate a smooth deployment experience.

Flowchart

Figure 4.3 shows a proposed flowchart of the processes of the approach for the proof-of-concepts tool. In this flow diagram, the user first access the website providing the feature model. The tool checks for validity issues and allocates all the intents for each feature. Once this step is done, we have generated the chatbot product line, and now, we will only need to make selections based on our product line. This selection will be again validated with the AAFM tool and then the chatbot will be assembled and deployed.

Figure 4.3: Flow Diagram of the User-Tool interaction

4.5. Components description

The proposed approach is designed to address the challenges of efficient chatbot generation and customization. This section presents an overview of the key components that constitute the approach. The approach encompasses the application engineering process, which focuses on analyzing product requirements, and the domain engineering process, which leverages domain expertise to identify reusable assets and define the product line. The core components of the architecture shown in Figure 4.4 include a database for storing relevant data, an Automated Analysis and Feature Modeling (AAFM) tool to work with feature models, a deployment server to host chatbot instances, a construction module to generate the software product line, and a configuration model to customize chatbot functionality. These components collectively contribute to the effective generation, management, and deployment of chatbots within the product line, ensuring flexibility and scalability in meeting diverse user requirements.

Figure 4.4: Abstract architecture for validating the proposal

- **Database:** The database component serves as a storage system for various entities related to the chatbot product line. It stores user data, chatbot configurations, intent information, and data from the software product line. The DB allows efficient retrieval, management, and persistence of these entities, enabling seamless data access for the other components.
- **AAFM:** The AAFM tool is an essential component for working with feature models in the chatbot product line. Provides functionalities for creating, editing, and validating feature models. The tool enables the representation and manipulation of features, their dependencies, and constraints, ensuring the consistency and correctness of the product line's configuration options.
- **Configuration Module:** The configuration module represents the selection and configuration of intentions for a particular chatbot instance within the product line. It allows users to choose from the available intents stored in the database and configure their inclusion in the generated chatbot. The configuration model enables customization and adaptation of the chatbot's functionality by selecting the desired intents for a specific chatbot instance.
- **Builder Module:** The construction module is responsible for generating chat-

bots based on the input provided by the user, including the feature model and reusable information. It utilizes the AAFM tool to validate and work with the feature model and leverages the SPL data stored in the database to construct the corresponding SPL of chatbots. The construction module automates the process of generating the chatbot product line based on the specified configuration.

- **Deployment Server:** The deployment server component handles the deployment of chatbots generated from the product line. It manages the hosting and distribution of chatbot instances to make them accessible to users. The deployment server ensures reliable and scalable deployment of chatbots, allowing for efficient interaction between users and the deployed chatbot instances.

4.6. Summary

Following this proposal, the development and deployment of chatbots could become more efficient and scalable. The preprocessing step ensures consistency in data input, while the featurization and chatbot product line generation enable the creation of customized chatbots. This approach minimizes redundant preprocessing efforts, as the information is stored centrally and can be easily selected and loaded into chatbots as needed. The key points of this proposal are based on:

- **Customization and adaptability:** The proposed approach emphasizes the customization and adaptability of chatbots within the same domain. Using the chatbot product line, it becomes possible to create chatbots tailored to specific domains while maintaining a consistent underlying structure. This flexibility enables each chatbot to have its own unique features and characteristics, catering to the specific needs and requirements of individual establishments.
- **Efficient knowledge management:** Centralized information storage in the chatbot product line promotes efficient knowledge management. Rather than spreading data across multiple sources, all relevant information is consolidated in one place. This consolidation simplifies the management and maintenance of the chatbot product line, making it easier to update and incorporate new information or features when needed.
- **Scalability and extensibility:** The proposed approach supports scalability and extensibility, allowing the addition of new chatbots within the same domain with minimal effort. For instance, in the previous example of restaurants, if new restaurants are introduced, it becomes a matter of configuring new chatbots based on the existing chatbot product line, reducing development time and resources. This scalability ensures that the proposed solution can accommodate future growth and expansion.
- **Consistency and branding:** By utilizing a chatbot product line, there is an opportunity to maintain consistency in branding and messaging across multiple chatbots. Standardized features and responses can be shared among chatbots. This consistency could improve the brand identity and foster familiarity for users who interact with different chatbots within the same domain.
- **Reduced development time and costs:** The proposed approach streamlines the

development process by eliminating redundant preprocessing steps and allowing the reuse of information. With the chatbot product line serving as a foundation, the time and costs associated with developing new chatbots can be reduced. This efficiency could allow organizations to allocate resources more effectively and focus on other critical aspects of chatbot deployment and management.

In conclusion, the processes proposed provide a structured approach to the definition, configuration, and deployment of chatbots. These processes collectively enable the systematic creation and deployment of chatbots within the product line, trying to provide a scalable and efficient approach. By defining a feature model and leveraging reusable assets, the product line architecture allows the derivation of multiple chatbot instances with varying features and functionalities. This not only could save development time, but also could ensure consistency and maintainability across the chatbot ecosystem. Furthermore, the use of a database, an AAFM tool, a deployment server, and a construction module streamlines the overall process flow and could the efficiency of chatbot generation and deployment. Integration of these components facilitates information management, feature validation, and automated deployment, making the entire process more manageable and effective.

Part IV

PROOF OF CONCEPTS

5. Tool implementation

5.1. Introduction

In this chapter, we present the validation of our proposed solution by implementing it as an API deployed in the cloud. The API serves as a powerful tool for generating chatbots based on our abstract architecture. By leveraging the technologies and tools that we will discuss, we demonstrate how the API facilitates the main processes involved in creating chatbots. These processes include the loading and extraction of information, chatbot configuration, and automated deployment. Through this validation, we showcase the practical implementation of our solution and its ability to generate chatbots efficiently and effectively. Moreover, in the appendix B there is a video demo of the tool that follows all the above steps.

5.2. Technologies

First, we will explore the technologies that will be used for the implementation of the approach processes. It is essential to emphasize that the choice of these technologies is based on their suitability for our project and the existing expertise. The selected technologies are not absolute and may vary depending on specific requirements and individual preferences. Although alternative technologies could enhance the capabilities of our tools, we have chosen those that align best with our objectives and resources. This chapter aims to provide an overview of the technologies and tools that will be utilized to bring our abstract architecture to life.

5.2.1 Database

When considering the selection of a database for our chatbot product line, we evaluated several options based on their suitability for our specific requirements. In this comparison, we will focus on MongoDB¹, MySQL², and PostgreSQL³, three widely used databases with distinct features and capabilities. Although both MySQL and PostgreSQL are well established and widely adopted in various applications, we have chosen MongoDB as the preferred database for our chatbot product line. MongoDB's document-oriented architecture and flexibility in handling dynamic data align more closely with the needs of our chatbot system. Furthermore, its scalability and high performance characteristics make it a suitable choice to accommodate the potential growth and demands of our chatbot product line.

¹<https://www.mongodb.com/>

²<https://www.mysql.com/>

³<https://www.postgresql.org/>

5.2.2 AAFM

For the AAFM, we have opted to use FLAMA. This decision was influenced by my previous experience and familiarity with the tool. It provides a comprehensive set of functionalities for analyzing and manipulating feature models, which are essential components of our chatbot product line. Using FLAMA, we can efficiently perform various tasks related to the validation of the feature model, the verification of consistency, and the exploration of configurations. Given my previous successful experiences using this tool in similar projects, the decision to utilize this tool was straightforward. The availability of code examples and the experience of working with FLAMA significantly reduce the learning curve and allows us to focus on implementing the specific requirements of our chatbot product line.

5.2.3 Configurator

When considering the technology to implement the configurator component of our chatbot product line, several options were evaluated. Among the contenders were Python Flask⁴, Ruby on Rails⁵, and Node.js with Express.js⁶. Ultimately, we decided to develop a Node.js Express.js API as the preferred choice. Node.js with Express.js excels in terms of performance and scalability. Its lightweight and minimalist design makes it well suited for building RESTful APIs efficiently. Additionally, the extensive npm package ecosystem associated with Node.js provides a wide range of libraries and modules that can further enhance the configurator's functionality and streamline development.

5.2.4 Builder

For the builder component of our chatbot product line, we chose to utilize Xatkit, an open source tool specifically designed to create chatbots. Xatkit offers a range of advantages that make it an excellent choice for our project. One of the key factors in choosing Xatkit was its powerful DSL (Domain-Specific Language) [45], which enables comprehensive customization of chatbot behavior. Additionally, Xatkit integrates seamlessly with NLP.js⁷, a well-known JavaScript-based natural language processing engine.

5.2.5 Deployment

For the deployment of our chatbots, we have chosen to use Docker⁸, a popular containerization platform. Docker offers several advantages that align with our project goals and requirements. One key benefit of Docker is its ability to encapsulate applications and their dependencies within containers. By containerizing our chatbots, we can ensure that they run consistently across different environments without being affected by variations in the underlying systems.

⁴<https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/2.3.x/>

⁵<https://rubyonrails.org/>

⁶<https://nodejs.org/es>

⁷<https://github.com/axa-group/nlp.js/>

⁸<https://www.docker.com/>

5.3. Implementation

This section provides an in-depth description of the implementation details of the proposed approach for efficient chatbot generation and reusability. Implementation encompasses various processes, including data preprocessing, feature modeling, chatbot product line generation, chatbot configuration, and chatbot deployment. Each process is crucial for achieving the desired result of contextually aware and domain-specific chatbots.

5.3.1 Data preprocessing

Data preprocessing is a crucial step in preparing the information for chatbot deployment. It involves cleaning the data, resolving inconsistencies, and ensuring its suitability for further processing. In the proposed approach, we have implemented two different formats for data upload: JSON and UVL.

Format standardization

JSON format is used to upload information artifacts, which consist of questions and the corresponding responses for each feature. For each feature in the chatbot product line, users are required to identify the questions that users could ask related to that feature. Then these questions are associated with their corresponding responses. The JSON structure provides a standardized format for capturing and organizing this information, enabling efficient processing and retrieval. On the other hand, UVL format is used for uploading the feature models. The feature model captures the different aspects or components of the chatbot and their relationships, facilitating easy configuration and customization. Excerpt 5.1 illustrates the code that manages this process.

```
1  const multer = require('multer');
2
3  // Define storage settings for uploaded files
4  const storage = multer.diskStorage({
5    destination: function (req, file, cb) {
6      cb(null, 'lines')
7    },
8    filename: function (req, file, cb) {
9      cb(null, file.originalname)
10   }
11 });
12
13 // Define file filter function
14 const fileFilter = function (req, file, cb) {
15   // check if the file ends with .uvl
16   if (!file.originalname.match(/\.(uvl|json)$/)) {
17     return cb(null, false, 'File must be a .uvl or .json file');
18   } else {
19     cb(null, true);
20   }
21 }
```

Code excerpt 5.1: Format standardization in the tool

Inconsistency resolution

In the data preprocessing stage, one of the key tasks is to resolve inconsistencies and ensure that each feature in the feature model is properly populated with the necessary information. To achieve this, the tool checks that for each feature defined in the feature model, corresponding intents and their associated questions and responses are provided in the information.json file. This ensures that if a feature is selected during the chatbot configuration process, the relevant intents will be loaded into the chatbot, allowing it to respond appropriately to user queries and requests. Excerpt 5.2 illustrates how the tool processes the data, verifying the consistency of the information.

```
1 // check we have info for all intents
2 if (intentsArray.length < result.length) {
3   res.status(400).json({ message: "Intent file does not contain all
4     needed info" });
5 }
6 // check all intents are in result
7 for (let i = 0; i < intentsArray.length; i++) {
8   const intent = intentsArray[i];
9   const found = result.find(element => element === intent.title);
10  if (found === undefined) {
11    res.status(400).json({ message: "Intent file contains info for an
12      intent not present in the model" });
13  }
```

Code excerpt 5.2: Consistency checks made by the tool

Data cleaning

After the necessary information has been processed and validated, the tool exports the clean data to the designated database. This ensures that the information is readily accessible for chatbot generation and configuration. Additionally, any unnecessary files or temporary data used during the data preprocessing stage are removed, streamlining the storage and organization of the chatbot's data assets. By performing data cleaning as part of the preprocessing step, the tool ensures that subsequent processes can operate efficiently on high-quality, consistent data.

5.3.2 Feature modeling

In the feature modeling stage, the user is required to model the variability of intents and produce a chatbot product line based on this model. The feature model serves as a blueprint to capture the different features and functionalities that chatbot products can possess.

Validity checking

To ensure the correctness of the feature model provided by the user, the tool uses a validation process. Specifically, the tool utilizes FLAMA, for making feature model validation. FLAMA checks the user-provided feature model for adherence to the defined syntax and semantics of the underlying variability modeling language, such as UVL.

By validating the feature model, the tool verifies its consistency and completeness, thus guaranteeing its suitability for deriving chatbot products. Excerpt 5.3 shows how the tool uses FLAMA to perform the validity check process.

```
1  const formData = new FormData();
2  formData.append('model', data, { filename: model.originalname });
3
4  const response = await fetch(FLAMA_API_URL + "/validate/model", {
5    method: 'POST',
6    body: formData,
7    headers: {
8      'Authorization': 'Bearer ${token}'
9    }
10 });
```

Code excerpt 5.3: FLAMA usage for model validity checking

Feature-information mapping

Once the feature model has been validated, the tool proceeds to associate each feature in the model with the corresponding information. This step involves mapping each feature to the relevant intents and their associated questions and responses. By establishing these connections, the tool ensures that the information is correctly aligned with the features defined in the feature model. This mapping process enables the seamless integration of feature-specific information into the subsequent stages of chatbot generation and configuration. Excerpt 5.4 illustrates how the tool maps the intents.

```
1  const intentsArray = [];
2  for (const intentName in intentsData) {
3    const intentData = intentsData[intentName];
4    const intentTraining = intentData.questions;
5    const intentResponse = intentData.answer;
6
7    intentsArray.push(newIntent);
```

Code excerpt 5.4: Feature-information mapping made by the tool

Integration of information input

All information, including the validated feature model and associated feature-specific data, is stored in the database. This centralized storage allows users to conveniently select the desired features when configuring chatbots. Users can simply choose the features they want to include in their chatbot and the tool will automatically load the corresponding information into the chatbot instance. By integrating the information input with the feature model, the tool simplifies the process of configuring chatbots based on the selected features, facilitating customization and adaptability for different chatbot instances.

5.3.3 Chatbot product line generation

Now, in order to produce our chatbot product line, we have to define both the feature model and the information.json file. Figure 5.1 shows an example of a feature model

and an information file based on the example of the restaurant chatbot product line made in earlier sections. In this feature model, we can see different types of ordering food, optional and exclusive facilities, and a shared menu.

Figure 5.1: Example of a feature model and information file

With this information, we can use the tool interface to create a brand new chatbot product line, as shown in Figure 5.2.

5.3.4 Chatbot configuration

The chatbot configuration process allows users to select the specific intents they want to include in their chatbot instance. By choosing the desired intents, users can customize the behavior and functionality of the chatbot to meet their specific needs and requirements.

Figure 5.2: Chatbot product line creation with the tool

Configuration interface

The configuration interface provided by the tool enables users to easily select the intents they want to load into their chatbot. Figure 5.3 illustrates an example of the configuration interface. To initiate the configuration process, users must provide the chatbot product line ID, which identifies the specific product line that contains the desired intents. They also need to specify the list of intents they want to include in their chatbot.

Figure 5.3: Chatbot configuration with the tool

Validity checking

Once the user completes the configuration, the tool performs a validity check to ensure that the generated chatbot satisfies all the defined restrictions and requirements. This validation step ensures that the selected intents are compatible with each other and adhere to the constraints specified in the feature model. Excerpt 5.5 shows this validity verification process. To perform the validity check, the tool leverages the FLAMA framework, which assesses the consistency and correctness of the configured chatbot. Any potential conflicts or inconsistencies are identified and flagged, enabling users to make necessary adjustments to their configuration.

```
1 const configPath = "../lines/" + pl._id + "/" + req.body.name + ".csv";
2 const configData = fs.readFileSync(configPath);
3 const blob2 = new Blob([configData], { type: 'text/csv' });
4 formData.append('configuration', blob2, 'configuration.csv');
5
6 const response = await fetch(FLAMA_API_URL + "/validate/configuration", {
7   method: 'POST',
8   body: formData,
9 });
```

Code excerpt 5.5: Feature-information mapping made by the tool

Automatic data loading

In the automatic data loading step, the configured and validated chatbot information is automatically loaded into the corresponding Dockerfile. The Dockerfile serves as a blueprint for building the chatbot application, ensuring that all selected intents and associated data are included in the final chatbot deployment. By automating the data loading process, the tool eliminates the need for manual intervention, reducing the risk of human error and ensuring the accuracy and completeness of the loaded data. The Dockerfile contains instructions for importing the necessary libraries, configuring the environment, and integrating the selected intents and their associated information. Figure 5.6 illustrates how the tool writes the chatbot information to a new Dockerfile.

```
1 const chatbotInfo = chatbot.toChatbot();
2 const intents = await Intent.find({ _id: { $in: chatbot.intents } });
3 const intentInfo = intents.map(intent => intent.toChatbot());
4
5 chatbotInfo.intents = intentInfo;
6 if (!fs.existsSync('./bots/${chatbot.id}')) {
7   fs.mkdirSync('./bots/${chatbot.id}');
8 }
9
10 fs.copyFileSync('./bots/Dockerfile', './bots/${chatbot.id}/Dockerfile');
```

Code excerpt 5.6: Chatbot generation process

Automatic compilation

In the automatic compilation step, the user initiates the compilation process, which generates the final chatbot application and prepares it for deployment. Once the user

triggers the compilation command, the tool utilizes the provided chatbot ID to locate the corresponding configuration and data files. The compilation process involves combining the chatbot configuration, selected intents, and associated data with the underlying chatbot framework and dependencies. The tool automatically handles the compilation steps, such as bundling the necessary libraries, optimizing the code, and packaging the application into a deployable format. Figure 5.4 illustrates how users compile chatbots with the tool interface.

The screenshot shows a web interface for compiling a chatbot. At the top, there is a header bar with the text "POST /api/v1/chatbots/mine/{chatbot_id}/compile Compile a chatbot by ID". Below the header, there is a section titled "Parameters" with a "Cancel" button. The main content area is a table with two columns: "Name" and "Description". The table contains one row with the following data:

Name	Description
chatbot_id * required string (path)	ID of the chatbot to compile

The value "64496b42be2a6a8b8e5f7e" is entered in the input field for the "chatbot_id" parameter. At the bottom of the interface, there are two buttons: "Execute" (highlighted in blue) and "Clear".

Figure 5.4: Chatbot compilation process

Upon successful compilation, the tool generates a Dockerfile that encapsulates the compiled chatbot application. This Dockerfile serves as a self-contained unit that can be easily deployed on various platforms and environments. The user can download the Dockerfile, which contains all the necessary components and configurations to run the chatbot application.

5.4. Results

With the help of Docker, we achieve easy deployment to any server or hosting platform, allowing for seamless integration of the chatbot into existing systems. Users can interact with the chatbot through an interface, posing questions or making requests. The chatbot takes advantage of NLP capabilities to understand and interpret user input, providing relevant and accurate responses. Figure 5.5 shows the functionality of two different chatbots based on the same product line, but different features.

One of the key advantages of our approach is the ability to generate multiple chatbots based on the chatbot product line. By selecting the desired features of the product line, users can customize each chatbot according to their specific needs. This flexibility allows for the creation of customized chatbots for different restaurants or entities while leveraging the shared features and information stored in the product line.

Furthermore, our approach promotes reusability and consistency between chatbot instances. The chatbot product line serves as a repository of reusable assets, such as intents and domain-specific information, which can be easily shared and reused. This not only enhances scalability, but also ensures consistency in chatbot behavior and responses.

Figure 5.5: Two chatbots from our restaurant product line

5.5. Threats to validity

Although the methodology presented in this project offers advantages in chatbot development and deployment, there are potential threats to the validity of the results. These threats should be considered when interpreting the findings:

1. NLP services: Integrating NLP utilities, such as the nlp.js server, introduces dependencies on the performance and accuracy of the underlying NLP algorithms. Variations in the performance of the NLP tools may affect the overall performance and quality of the chatbot's natural language understanding and processing.
2. System performance: Although the presented methodology demonstrates the generation and deployment of chatbots, the scalability of the approach may pose challenges when dealing with larger, more complex chatbot configurations or high-volume user interactions. Performance issues or limitations may arise when scaling the system to handle increased user demands.

5.6. Summary

Using a product line approach, we were able to identify and define features, intents, and relevant information, establishing a solid foundation for chatbot generation. Utilizing FLAMA for validation ensured that user configurations adhered to predefined rules and constraints, preventing inconsistent or conflicting configurations. Xatkit has

been proven to be an effective tool for creating chatbots based on the product line specification. With the compilation process, the chatbot was generated and provided in the form of a Dockerfile, which facilitated easy deployment of the chatbot on different servers and operating systems. The flexibility and portability offered by Docker allowed for hassle-free deployment in various environments.

Moreover, the incorporation of NLP utilities, demonstrated in Figure 5.5, showcased the improved capabilities of the chatbot in understanding and interpreting user input. By connecting to our dedicated nlp.js server, the chatbots were able to take advantage of advanced natural language processing algorithms, resulting in improved accuracy and context-awareness in their responses. Overall, the approach presented in this project opens up opportunities to generate and deploy additional chatbots using existing information. By simply selecting the desired intents, FLAMA can validate the configuration, and the chatbot can be generated and deployed using Docker. This streamlined process can reduce the development time and effort required to create new chatbots, making it a scalable and efficient solution. The presented approach sets the foundation for future advancements and applications in the field of chatbot development and deployment.

Part V

CONCLUSIONS

6. Conclusions and future work

6.1. Conclusions

Through a literature review, we identified a viable research question that addressed the challenges of defining and reusing information in the development of chatbots. Our investigation led us to propose a systematic approach to chatbot generation, leveraging the concepts of feature models, domain engineering, and configuration. Using suitable technologies and tools, we implemented a proof-of-concept solution that validated our approach.

Through the design and implementation of an architecture for generating pre-trained chatbots, we have addressed the identified problem and provided a solution that leverages the reuse of domain artifacts. Our proof-of-concept tool has demonstrated the successful generation, automatic validation, and deployment of chatbots. Additionally, we have enabled the download, control, and integration of chatbots with NLP servers, enhancing their functionality and user interaction. In addition to technical achievements, this project has also served as a valuable opportunity for personal growth, allowing me to learn from respected advisors, make a meaningful contribution to the research field, and improve my research skills.

Despite making progress in the research project, it is important to recognize that not all tasks were completed as originally planned. Specifically, Task 8, Task 9, and Task 10, which involved performing experiments, analyzing results, and comparing the developed approach with existing methods, were not completed as intended. The lack of a comprehensive comparison and performance evaluation of the developed approach compared to other tools was primarily due to time constraints and resource limitations. This was due to the fact that a new task arose, which was not initially identified, when the developed approach was submitted to SISTEDES¹, a national conference on software engineering. In response to the submission, additional efforts were required to prepare a research paper and a tool demonstration. These efforts required further refinement and enhancement of the tool to show its capabilities and potential impact. We are pleased to report that our submission was accepted, providing an opportunity to present our work and receive valuable feedback from the research community.

Although the initial objectives of directly comparing the developed approach with existing methods could not be fully realized, the recognition and acceptance of our work in SISTEDES could validate the relevance and potential contributions of the project. This demonstrates the practical applicability and value of the developed approach, despite the absence of a formal comparative evaluation. Moving forward, it is recommended that future research efforts allocate adequate resources and time for a rigorous performance evaluation and comparison with existing methods to further validate and refine the developed approach. Figure 6.1 shows the differences between the initial planning and the actual time planning.

¹<https://sistedes2023.uclm.es/>

Figure 6.1: Initial planning vs results

6.2. Future work

To ensure continuous improvement and progress of the project, two potential areas for future work have been identified. These areas represent challenges that, although not addressed in the current stage, are crucial to enhancing the capabilities and effectiveness of the proposed solution. In this section, we will outline the key problems that require further attention. By addressing these challenges, we aim to further refine the chatbot generation process, enhance the tool functionality, and explore new possibilities for its application in real-world scenarios.

6.2.1 Feature identification

During the course of our research, we have identified different approaches for feature identification in the chatbot's dialog, each with varying levels of complexity. The aim of feature identification is to enhance user interaction with the chatbot. We propose two potential approaches for further exploration.

- **Model-based approach:** This strategy involves mapping specific features of the chatbot to the corresponding intents in the underlying model. By incorporating features such as menu, takeaway, and lounge into the model, the chatbot gains the capability to respond effectively to user queries related to these specific topics. The proof-of-concept implementation of our chatbot has utilized this approach, demonstrating its effectiveness in handling predefined feature-based interactions. Further investigation can focus on refining the model-based approach by incorporating additional features and optimizing intent classification.
- **State machine approach:** A more advanced option for feature identification is the use of a state machine. This approach involves defining a set of states and transitions that capture the flow of conversation and dynamically identify the active

feature during the interaction. However, given the current scope of our Master’s Thesis, we were unable to delve into the complexities of this methodology. However, we strongly recommend considering the state-machine approach for future research. It has the potential to enhance the chatbot’s ability to handle complex dialogues and adapt to evolving user requirements.

- Machine learning-based approach: The use of machine learning techniques, such as natural language processing (NLP) and supervised algorithms, offers another promising avenue for feature identification. This approach involves training a model on a labeled dataset that associates user input with specific features. The model can then predict the relevant features based on the input text. This approach provides flexibility and adaptability as the chatbot learns from user interactions and improves its feature identification capabilities over time. However, it requires a significant amount of labeled training data and ongoing model training to achieve accurate results.

By exploring these alternative approaches, future research can contribute to the development of more sophisticated chatbot systems that provide a seamless and personalized user experience.

6.2.2 Chatbot product line evolution

One of the challenges we face with this proposal is maintaining up-to-date information in the chatbot product line. For example, consider a scenario where the closing time of a restaurant changes from 9 PM to 12 PM due to the pandemic. Updating the product line is a straightforward process, ensuring that all new chatbots generated will have updated information. However, a problem arises with the existing chatbots that still have the old closing time of 9 PM. In order to keep them up-to-date, each individual chatbot needs to be identified and updated with the new information.

In the literature, we can find a concept closely related to the dynamic management of change that we require. These are known as Dynamic Software Product Lines (DSPLs) [32], which allow the activation or deactivation of specific features to adapt the configuration in production. If a specific restaurant no longer has a lounge, DSPLs provide support to disable the corresponding intent. Similarly, if the closing time of a restaurant changes, DSPLs propose architectures that proactively listen for such changes and propagate them accordingly.

References [3] and [16] provide context on what DSPLs are, how they differ from Software Product Lines (SPLs), and the theoretical foundations of their functioning. Reference [6] proposes an architecture for maintaining up-to-date DSPLs, including mechanisms for information synchronization. For the management of change, we can consider three different implementations:

- Implementation A: When updating the information of a specific product in our chatbot product line, the initial proposal would involve destroying the chatbot, regenerating it, and redeploying it. However, this approach is contrary to the principles of product line engineering.
- Implementation B: When updating the information of a specific product in our

chatbot product line, we can leverage the mechanisms proposed by DSPLs. This typically involves having a "listener" that detects changes in the product line's intents. The listener then identifies the chatbots in production that need to be updated and sends them the new information, enabling one-to-one mapping of the old intent to the new intent. This approach avoids the need to destroy and redeploy the chatbot.

- Implementation C: If there is a need for continuous and massive change management, it would be beneficial to define a network of core intents. In feature models, core features are those that are present in all products. In our case, they represent the common intents shared by all chatbots. We can create a parent chatbot that contains all the relevant information for the core intents, and child chatbots with their own specific intents. When updating the child chatbot's information, only that specific chatbot needs to be modified. Similarly, when updating the common information in the parent chatbot (as the children reference it), a single change is sufficient.

These different implementation approaches provide flexibility in managing changes in the chatbot product line, and future work can explore its effectiveness and efficiency in different scenarios and domain contexts.

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B. Resources

B.1. Code repositories

- Master's Thesis: <https://github.com/joszamama/xatkit-spl-api>
- FLAMA: <https://github.com/flamapy/>
- Xatkit: <https://github.com/xatkit-bot-platform/xatkit>

B.2. Video demos

- Master's Thesis Demo: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2mnxehWpxWI>

B.3. Deployment

- Master's Thesis Deployment: <https://xatkit-spl-api.onrender.com/>

B.4. Installation guide

- Master's Thesis Guide: <https://github.com/joszamama/xatkit-spl-api#getting-started>

B.5. User manual

- Master's Thesis Manual: <https://github.com/joszamama/xatkit-spl-api#using-the-tool>

C. Glossary of terms

- **Application Engineering:** Process that involves analyzing and defining the specific requirements, features, and functionalities of individual applications within a software product line. It focuses on tailoring and configuring the product line to meet the specific needs and goals of a particular application.
- **Chatbot:** A computer program designed to simulate conversation with human users, often used for customer support or information retrieval.
- **CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment):** A software development practice that involves regularly integrating code changes into a shared repository and automating the deployment of software to production environments.
- **Configuration Model:** A representation of the selected features and their configurations within a software product line, specifying the variations and options available for generating individual products.
- **Domain Engineering:** The process of identifying and analyzing the commonalities and variabilities within a specific domain to create reusable assets for a software product line.
- **DSL (Domain-Specific Language):** A programming language designed for a specific domain or problem area, providing concise and expressive syntax for addressing specific requirements.
- **Feature Model:** A representation of the configurable features and their relationships in a software product line, often depicted as a tree-like structure.
- **Intent:** In the context of chatbots, an intent represents the goal or intention of a user's input, such as making a reservation or asking for help.
- **NLP (Natural Language Processing):** A field of artificial intelligence that focuses on the interaction between computers and human language, enabling chatbots to understand and generate human language.
- **Software Product Line:** A set of software products that share a common set of features and are developed from a common set of assets.